

Opportunities of Smart Aquaculture and Eco-farming Integration in Palm Oil Mill Effluent Bioremediation and Phycoremediation System for Environmental Sustainability

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Abstract: The increasing production of palm oil mill effluent (POME), which contains pollutants, causes serious environmental problems. The POME treatment can be carried out biologically process by using microalgae, it's called phycoremediation. Biorefineries produced from microalgae biomass cultivated on POME have been widely observed by researchers and found to be very promising. Another alternative to utilizing biomass from treated POME is smart aquaculture and eco-farming. There is no published literature on the integration of these two systems. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to provide the available literature on bioremediation and phycoremediation of POME, to assess the potential reuse of POME treated for integrated smart aquaculture and eco-farming to highlight scientific and regulatory gaps and implementation obstacles. Based on the data and information gathered regarding the large amount of POME in Indonesia and other countries, the adoption of large-scale smart aquaculture and eco-farming is particularly helpful, as monitoring can be done promptly and efficiently. The implementation of new model smart farming systems in developing nations requires greater support from the government at the low farm level and the business sector. This review can be utilized to advance the state of the art in environmental sustainability of POME remediation systems.

Keywords: biorefinery; bioremediation; microalgae; Palm Oil Mill Effluent; phycoremediation; smart aquaculture; eco-farming

1. Introduction

Eukaryotic algae, including microalgae and cyanobacteria, that provide an alternative to currently employed traditional biological treatments that are energy-intensive and ecologically favorable for the treatment of wastewater¹). Bioremediation is an activity system that uses biological processes to reduce, degrade, modify, eliminate, immobilize, detoxify, mineralize, or transform pollutant concentrations to non-harmful or non-toxic levels²). In addition to being a sustainable source of

biomass, CO₂ fixation using microalgae in wastewater treatment is efficient and practical³). Microalgae can consume carbon, organic, and inorganic components in wastewater treatment, such as N and P, for growth, reducing the concentration of these elements in the wastewater. Phycoremediation is defined as the use of microalgae to treat wastes or wastewater³).

Microalgae cultivation media containing nutrients is a significant economic component with an impact on the long-term viability of microalgae cells in culture. The cost of widely used synthetic media is high, hence alternate

media alternatives must be sought. This alternative media can come from industrial or household wastewater. Palm oil, also known as Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME), is one source of organic waste from industry that can become pollutants to the environment. The key benefit of wastewater treatment utilizing microalgae is the production of O₂, which is required for heterotrophic bacteria to biodegrade carbon compounds. Although it is difficult to compare the effects of microalgae culture in wastewater treatment, numerous studies have shown that microalgae formation can help with nutrient removal in wastewater⁴⁾.

Indonesia has become the world's largest producer of Crude Palm Oil (CPO), with a total production of 32 million tons, accounting for approximately 46.6% of worldwide CPO production as the palm oil sector expands. The demand for CPOs in the global market is escalating. According to Figures from worldwide, the anticipated global demand for CPO in 2020 is 95.7 million tons. Waste production is rising in tandem with the demand for CPO⁵⁾. According to the study's findings, processing 1 (one) tonne of oil palm Fresh Fruit Bunches (FFB) will result in waste that includes empty oil palm fruit bunches weighing up to 23% or about 230 kg, shell waste weighing up to 6.5% or about 65 kg, and palm sludge (wet decanter solid) that weighs up to 4% (or 40 kg), fiber that weighs up to 13% or about 130 kg, and liquid waste that weighs up Studying the biological treatment provided by microalgae is crucial due to the rise in POME.

Palm oil or CPO is the mainstay of foreign exchange earning commodity for Indonesia from the agro-industry sector, which produces around 85-90% of the total world palm oil production. Riau Province has a palm oil plantation area of 2.8 million hectares with total CPO production, which has increased from the previous year, namely 9.1 million tons in 2017 and 9.8 million tons in 2018⁵⁾. The expanding Indonesian palm oil industry will generate an increasing amount of liquid waste. POME contains carbon and nitrogen that can be used as nutrients for microalgae growth as well as for pollutant removal in wastewater⁶⁾.

According to recent reports, oil palm production is wreaking havoc on the environment, particularly in Southeast Asia. It has been reported that the POME wastewater treatment system produces pollutants that can damage the environment.⁵⁾ POME bioremediation and phycoremediation have been widely observed by researchers. These procedures produce important biorefineries such as biodiesel and other bioenergy. Many have researched microalgae cultivation using POME wastewater media, but most of them are still on a laboratory scale.⁴⁾ For this reason, it is necessary to evaluate the research results on the potential of microalgae in POME processing and sustainability.

The possible issue is that it is uneconomical because

further processes are required before it can be used, which demands a large cost, so the price of biorefinery becomes expensive. As a solution to the challenge, this study proposes another method for employing collected microalgae biomass for fish feed in an integrated system. Furthermore, aquaculture's liquid waste can be used as agricultural fertilizer. This smart aquaculture and eco-farming concept is quite profitable. This integration system of POME remediation has no literature that publishes such study results, therefore the concept design that will be developed is the originality of the role of microalgae with POME medium in environmental sustainability. Reuse of POME treated for integrated smart aquaculture and eco-farming to highlight scientific and regulatory gaps and implementation obstacles.

The objectives of this study are to provide the available literature on bioremediation and phycoremediated POME, to assess the potential reuse of POME treated for integrated smart aquaculture and eco-farming to highlight scientific and regulatory gaps and implementation obstacles. The studies carried out covered the diversity of microalgae found in POME, selected microalgae capable of growing in POME to produce useful ingredients for biorefinery, and methods of pollutant removal processes in POME. In addition, the study then discussed the potential for sustainable aquaculture, and eco-farming as an environmental sustainability contribution.

2. Characteristics of POME

Coconut industry liquid waste Palm oil mill effluent (POME) includes a high concentration of organic compounds that can damage groundwater and bodies of water. When organic contaminants are large enough to enter streams, they can degrade water quality and diminish the carrying capacity of plants and the surrounding aquatic ecosystem. Reduced environmental carrying capacity causes the death of aquatic organisms, which slows the growth of other aquatic plants and increases odor, making it an ideal breeding ground for bacteria, both pathogenic bacteria (bacteria that cause disease) until it grows and grows and apathogenic bacteria (non-producing bacteria that can cause disease). Concentrate BOD (Biological Oxygen Demand) and TSS (Total Suspended Solids) waste from the palm oil mill that was released directly into the environment and does not fulfill quality standards, is what you get⁴⁾.

Characteristic chemicals and pollutants of POME are listed in Table 1 which summarizes the organic chemical properties. Additionally, non-organic chemical properties and heavy metal concentrations are given Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), and Zinc (Zn) which exceed the requirement threshold and cause toxic pollution to the environment. The role of microalgae in eliminating heavy metals, which are harmful contaminants, is critical in

combating environmental pollution^{7,8)}.

Heavy metal content was determined using silver nanoparticles⁹⁾. This approach is suitable for POME that contains heavy metals. Polysulfone/chitosan/polyvinyl

alcohol integrated composite membranes can also be used to extract heavy metals like mercury. Polyvinyl alcohol integral composite membranes¹⁰⁾.

Table 1: POME chemical and pollutants characteristic

Parameter	Unit	Range	Standard discharge limits (mg/L)
Protein*	g/L	4.2 – 6.0	-
Carbohydrate*	g/L	28.10 – 30.30	-
Total sugar*	g/L	1.5-3.	-
Fiber*	g/L	0.7-2.3	-
Fat*	g/L	6.00-7.20	-
Ash*	g/L	6.50–9.70	-
Nitrogen**	mg/L	180-1400	10
Phosphate**	mg/L	37.175	-
Phenol**	mg/L	≤0.0001	-
Potassium**	g/L	1.459	-
Sulphate**	g/L	1.032	-
Ammonia**	mg/L	125	10
Iron (Fe)**	mg/L	1757	1.0
Manganese (Mn)**	mg/L	62	1.0
Zinc (Zn)**	mg/L	1075	1.0
COD ***	mg/L	40000 – 90000	50
BOD ***	mg/L	15000 – 30000	20
Suspended solid ***	mg/L	50000– 54000	50
Oil and grease	mg/L	130-18000	10
pH***		3-5	6-9

Ref. *¹¹⁾, **¹²⁾, ***¹³⁾

3. Bioremediation and Phycoremediation in Removing POME Pollutants

In the removal of POME contaminants, bioremediation and phytoremediation are used. The bioremediation process begins with the removal of contaminants by microorganisms, specifically bacteria. Microalgae will use the byproducts of bacteria's breakdown of organic material to thrive. Meanwhile, microalgae remove hazardous heavy metal contaminants that bacteria are unable to ingest and break down. Microalgae cells store heavy metals. The process of microalgae absorbing hazardous heavy metal contaminants is known as phycoremediation^{14,15)}. Figure 1 depicts the variety of indigenous microalgae kinds found in POME. Figure 2 depicts the interaction process of bacteria and microalgae in cleanup.

Aside from bioremediation, the biomass and value products obtained during WW treatment make phycoremediation more suited and superior to all others¹⁶⁾. Microalgae might be used to remove all toxins from wastewater, and high-value metabolites and chemicals generated from algal biomass could be used in industrial applications, increasing the value of waste streams⁷⁾.

4. Diversity of Indigenous Microalgae in POME

The microalgae consortium is a mixture of various

microalgae species that naturally live together with various other microorganisms, such as bacteria^{17,18)}. A report from the research bacteria, namely *Bacillus* sp. POME microalgae consortium species have been isolated and identified^{19,20)}. The species diversity of the microalgae consortium is presented in Figure 1.

Microalgae consortium culture has faster growth and higher biomass than monoculture²¹⁾, with high biomass growth, will produce high lipid content as well^{22,23)}. Not only does the microalgae consortium have bioenergy potential, but it can also remove nutrients from wastewater^{24,25)}. The consortium of indigenous microalgae showed better growth and stability than microalgae monocultures, and could remove more than 98% COD in milk wastewater^{26,27)}. The COD levels in wastewater decrease along with the activity of microalgae that produce oxygen from the photosynthesis process^{28,29)}. In this study, a semi-continuous culture technique was carried out by changing the culture with new nutrients within a certain period. Time biomass productivity will increase along with the ratio of nutrients added to the microalgae culture³⁰⁾. Semi-continuous culture techniques increased biomass production by 38.5% with a biomass yield of 7.51±0.22 gr, while batch culture was 6.53±0.16 g³¹⁾.

Fig 1: Morphology of the diversity of microalgae and cyanobacteria species isolated from POME wastewater ¹⁷⁾

The adaptation phase was not seen in every treatment, because the microalgae cells that were inserted into each flat-photobioreactor came from cultures that were in the exponential phase, so the microalgae cells were fast in growing and dividing, states that the adaptation phase usually occurs when the inoculum is inoculated into a new medium with different chemical components. Indigenous microalgae consortia do not require a long adaptation. Time in their growth, so the microalgae cells will quickly enter the exponential phase ³²⁾.

5. Interaction of Microalgae and Bacteria in Wastewater Treatment

Wastewater treatment with microalgae is a green process that can eliminate pollution^{33,34)}. Several species of

microalgae have the potential to process POME as *Scenedesmus acutus*, *Scenedesmus acuminatus*, *Scenedesmus dimorphus*, *Scenedesmus rubescens*, and *Chlorella vulgaris*; because through photosynthesis, microalgae process POME to produce biomass by utilizing nitrogen and phosphorus compounds present in POME ¹⁷⁾. Figure 1 provides an illustration of the wastewater treatment process by microalgae and bacteria to produce biomass, both microalgae and bacteria. The two microorganisms interact where microalgae produce oxygen from photosynthesis with wastewater nutrients ^{35,36)}. Furthermore, bacteria utilize oxygen for their metabolic activities. These activities generate carbon dioxide, nitrogen, phosphorus, vitamins, and other substances that are used in the growth of microalgae

(Figure 2).

Because the microalgae biomass produced has the potential to become a major source of biofuel, using microalgae for POME processing is very cost-effective^{37,38}. Microalgae with lipid content of more than 40% are

very potential for biofuel. The results of the research above (Table 1) show that the species of *Tetraselmis suecica* and *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*, with lipid content of 68% and 68% have the most potential for biofuel raw materials.

Fig. 2: Schematic of interaction and molecular exchange between microalgae and bacteria in wastewater treatment.

Another benefit of microalgae is that they can be grown on ground that is not suitable for agriculture^{39,40}. Microalgae also can reduce BOD and COD from POME, thereby reducing pollution^{41,42}. POME has a wide and profitable application in microalgae cultivation. This is because using microalgae can reduce not only the nutrient content of POME; but also the resulting biomass, which can be used as a biorefinery source with added value. POME-grown microalgae are high in lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates, and can be used as feed and fuel. Another advantage, microalgae produce material that has potential value if used for compounds of biofuels and bioactive that benefit the energy and pharmaceutical industries.

6. Factors of Microalgae Limiting Growth in POME

The growth of microalgae is supplied by media containing nutrients according to their life needs. POME ponds contain nitrogen, phosphorus, and carbon, which is a nutrient essential for microalgae growth^{43,44}. In addition to nutrients from POME, light intensity, glucose concentration, and carbon dioxide concentration can boost microalgae growth and lipid content⁴. Much research on POME is used for microalgae media and the conclusion is that POME contains the nutrients needed by microalgae growth which are cultivated in open ponds with sufficient sunlight for photosynthesis.

Several variables, particularly photosynthesis, play an important role in microalgae growth requirements. Thus, carbon dioxide concentration and light intensity will be the primary factors that can influence microalgae growth. The effect of the two limiting factors for the microalgae growth was studied, as illustrated in Figure 1⁴⁵. According to the findings of this investigation, microalgae growth is directly

related to light intensity⁴⁶. High carbon dioxide concentrations cause the medium to become acidic, reducing photosynthetic activity and slowing growth rate. The ideal CO₂ concentration was discovered 12.5%⁴⁷. The maximum lipid production of *Ettlia* sp. YC001, on the other hand, was discovered to be below 0.05% CO₂ concentration and 400 E/m²/s light intensity⁴⁸. Furthermore, at different microalgae loads, green light produced the most photosynthetic activity and the highest rate of oxygen production⁴⁹.

Microalgae have a quick cell multiplication time and a flexible metabolism. Most are photoautotrophs, but due to changes in conditions and environment, many species undergo metabolic changes and become heterotrophs. The energy source for microalgae to carry out photosynthesis is carbon dioxide and carbon in organic molecules⁵⁰. POME ponds that are in a flooded condition, because wastewater is discharged into the pond with no flow, will promote the growth of microalgae. On the other hand, if there is water movement, it will interfere with the expansion of microalgae. Only in a calm stream can microalgae grow. Table 2 shows the range of optimum conditions for the growth of microalgae using POME.

Table 2: Environmental factors microalgae cultivation using POME³⁴

Parameters	Range	Optimum
Temperature (°C)	17-28	20-25
Salinity (mg/L)	13,000-30,000	22,000-25,000
Photoperiod light and dark)	-	16:8 (Minimum) 24 h (Maximum)
pH	7.0-9.0	8.2-8.7
Rate of CO ₂	1-4%	1% of volume di air
Nutrient	-	N:P (16:1)and Silicon

7. Case Study of POME Bioremediation

In the last few decades, numerous approaches for treating POME have been documented. Anaerobic systems commonly utilized in POME degradation include tank digestion and facultative ponds, tank digestion and mechanical aeration, physicochemical and biological

treatment, and decanter and facultative ponds. However, these systems have some downsides, including greenhouse gas emissions, long retention times, inconsistency in nutrient removal, and enormous land area needs⁵¹⁾. This study only presents an update on the results of POME bioremediation research for the last 4 years which can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Case study of POME bioremediation

Microorganism	Infrastructure	Pollutants reduction	Ref.
Meyerozyma guilliermondii	Flask experiments under aerobic condition	As a result, this strain is appropriate to be used in the remediation of POME.	51)
The chicken droppings and cow dung	clean plastic containers	The bacteria, mold, and yeast are useful in rehabilitation of POME-polluted soil and possibly	52,53)
Microorganisms found in cow dung included Proteus, Bacillus, Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas, Micrococcus, and Corynebacterium, as well as Fusarium, Aspergillus, Penicillium, Geothricum, and Mucor fungus species. Candida sp. yeast.	There are two different plastic containers. Set A included the POME-contaminated soil (PCS), whereas set B was augmented (amended) with 100g of dried and marshed cow dung.	Cowdung microorganisms have the potential to break down organic contaminants in the POME-contaminated soil.	54)
Aspergillus niger	Lab scale	<i>A. niger</i> has been shown to be 70% effective at removing COD.	55)
Anaerobic microorganism	Ponding system	success implementation of bioremediation and its challenges.	56)

8. Pre-Treatment of POME for Microalgae Cultivation

Before using POME for microalgae cultivation, it must be pre-treated. POME pre-treatment processes include thermal, chemical, mechanical, and biological processes. POME pre-treatment, such as coagulation and absorption processes, can increase sunlight penetration during the microalgae culture process in the POME system⁵⁷⁾. Rice flour and tapioca flour can be used in the coagulation process. In contrast, the absorption process can be carried out by utilizing activated carbon derived from palm shell biomass. This is an excellent way to repurpose the biomass generated by the palm oil industry.

POME pre-treatment with chemicals or activated carbon before microalgae are cultivated for thickening and absorption of color. Turbidity of wastewater can be reduced by adding activated carbon; so that microalgae can carry out photosynthesis more effectively. Activated carbon was reported to microalgae growth⁵⁸⁾.

Activated carbon generated from palm kernel shells has been shown to reduce turbidity by up to 83.33%, COD by up to 83.91%, and suspended solids by up to 92.30%. This decrease was higher than the coagulation procedure with rice and tapioca flour. However, the absorption process with activated carbon is longer than the coagulant

process⁴⁰⁾. The dark color of POME is caused by lignocellulosic plant components which contain lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose as well as carbohydrate components, namely hexoses, and pentoses. Heat-acid treatment is another way of POME pre-treatment to reduce dark color⁴¹⁾. The carbohydrate content in POME was broken down into glucose, the acid-heat pre-treatment method hydrogen. POME lignin dissolves easily in acid during the pre-treatment process⁵⁹⁾.

POME pre-treatment will help improve the microalgae growth process to produce sugars to be used as a medium. The pre-treatment process by removing the lignin that causes the dark color, provides an opportunity for more light to enter the media for the photosynthesis process to increase the microalgae growth. As a result, the use of POME for microalgae culture is feasible, and must be processed first to reduce BOD, COD, turbidity, and suspended solids to maximize POME utilization of microalgae. A new method called autoclaving was used, which resulted in increased yield and productivity of microalgae biomass to treat wastewater⁴¹⁾. At the same time treating wastewater with pre-treatment similar to autoclaving, centrifugation, and filtration, but this method requires energy for the process⁶⁰⁾. Several studies reported that microalgae cultivation in POME media was found to accumulate high levels of lipids. Pretreatment was

evaluated using several parameters, including pH, particle size, stirring speed, and POME dose.

9. Case Study of POME Phycoremediation by Tolerant Microalgae

Microalgae using POME media in this study were grown

in reactors with the necessary infrastructure to monitor their growth optimally. Microalgae cultivation can be done in two types of reactors: horizontal and vertical photobioreactors and open raceway ponds. Table 4 below summarizes the results of microalgae research with various growth process methods.

Table 4: Case study of POME pollutants removal by tolerant microalgae and produce biomass

Source of POME/concentration	Microalgae	Infrastructure cultivation	Pollutants reduction and Product/output	Ref.
POME from Waste Water Treatment Process pond with COD concentration 250 mg/L	<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i> , <i>Botryococcus seditiosus</i> , <i>Tetraselmis</i> sp, <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i> .	Room temperature Light intensity illumination continuous $\pm 15 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{x}^{-1}$	<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i> is the predominant species. It has the highest biomass and lipid productivity. Reduce COD and BOD	61)
POME diluted 50% + 1 g/L urea	<i>Chlorella</i> sp.	Laboratory scale. Temperature 28 °C	<i>Chlorella</i> sp showed a higher specific growth rate (0.066/day), at 50% POME 1gr/L urea,	62)
POME extracted from an anaerobic pond and diluted by 40%	<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	Laboratory scale Light intensity 4000 – 6000 Lx	POME has the potential to be used as an microalgae medium due to the reduction of external nutrients such as NaHCO ₃ , urea, and micronutrients. The benefits of clean treated POME after algae biomass harvesting. Saved 50% on synthetic nutrients while producing 5.93gr/l wet biomass for 9 days.	63)
POME from Waste Water Treatment Process	<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	1000 ml Erlenmeyer. Lighting for 24 hours using TL lamp.	The addition of 200 mg/l NaHCO ₃ results in the best nutrient composition. C,N,P levels in the media fell from 20.60% to 84.69%, 87.52% to 93.74%, and 29.44% to 76.66% at the end of cultivation.	64)
POME from the Waste Water Treatment Process Pond, undiluted	<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	3 L PBR (Photobioreactor) Temperature: 24-26 °C, mixing speed: 60 rpm 8:16 light jam (T:G) pH 6,5 – 7,5 150 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{x}^{-1}$ light intensity	POME was diluted ten times to lessen the shadowing effects on the growth of microalgae. Under continuous illumination, the highest amount of biomass (39.41 g/L) and lipid productivity (42 mg/L.d) were obtained.	65)
POME was 1% diluted	<i>Arthrospira platensis</i>	Outdoor tank with 10 L culture media in a 20 L tank	<i>A. platensis</i> can be cultured in 1% v/v fresh POME without compromising its growth or pigment production.	66)
POME with a COD concentration of 250 mg/L from the Waste Water	<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Photobioreactor HPBR 5 L with impeller turbine	A high microalgae growth rate (1.80 d1) was seen at 250 mg COD/L of substrate	67)

Treatment Process Pond.		Temperature: 30 °C Light intensity: 4 lamp @ 32 W continuous white fluorescent light cahaya fluoresense (24 jam) Germany, Philip C:N = 100:6		
POME from the Waste Water Treatment Process Pond with a COD concentration of 250 mg/L	<i>Chlamydomonas incerta</i>	Laboratory scale Temperayure 30 °C Light intensity 15 mol m ⁻² x -1	The cells developed slightly rough and corrugated textures, and some particles were discovered on the cell wall's surface. POME is a promising approach for either natural environmental treatment or as a high-lipid-content raw material for biofuel production.	68)
500 mL POME was diluted in 400 mL deionization water.	<i>Chlorella</i> sp	Laboratory scale	The mass transfer of CO ₂ from the gas phase into the liquid phase is the main area for improvement in order to increase the percentage of CO ₂ recovered.	69)
POME with a COD concentration of 130 mg/L from the Waste Water Treatment Process Pond	<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	Laboratory scale	The biomass contained lipid (39.9%) and carbohydrate (41.03%), which could be used as a biofuel source.	28)
POME with a COD concentration of 250 mg/L from the Waste Water Treatment Process Pond	<i>Chlamydomonas incerta</i>	Laboratory scale	The maximum biomass productivity and specific growth rate for the 16/8 cycle were 0.122 for the 24/0 L/D cycle. COD removal was 88%, TN removal was 97.3, and TP removal was 99.8%.	70)
POME has been pre-treated.	<i>Coelastrella</i> sp. <i>Chlamydomonas</i> sp. and <i>Scenedesmus</i> sp.	Laboratory scale	These native microalgal species have a high potential for cultivated in POME, phycoremediation and CO ₂ biofixation.	71)
Following the aerobic treatment method, higher POME concentrations were obtained and kept at 20°C.	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i> and <i>Chromochloris zofingiensis</i>	Laboratory scale	POME has the potential to be used microalgae cultivation to produce astaxanthin.	72)
5% anaerobic digested POME + 0.075% NPK + sea water	<i>Isochrysis</i> sp.	Photobioreactor, outdoor	Produce higher biomass, lipid, fatty acid content than microalgae cultivated indoor laboratory.	73)
10% POME + sea water	<i>Nannochloropsis . oculate</i> and <i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>	Culture in the laboratory	39% lipid; 29.24% SFA, 9.07% PUFA, and 93.6% COD removal	74)
POME 150 mg/L COD	<i>C. vulgaris</i>	Batch culture in laboratory	Produce lipid, carbohydrate, and reduce COD..	29)
POME at a concentration of 250 mg/L COD	<i>B.braunii</i>	Laboratory culture flask.	Produce carbohydrate and lipid.	29)
1% raw fresh POME +	<i>S. platensis</i>	Green house	Produce phycocyanin,	66)

commercial nutrient		cultivation;	carotenoid, and chlorophyll in biomass.	
10% POME digested + water	<i>C. vulgaris</i>	Culture in the laboratory flask batch cultivation; 10 k lux light for 24 hours.	Produce lipid, protein, carbohydrate; and linolenic acid.	⁷⁵⁾

The concept of integrating smart aquaculture and eco-farming in a post-POME phytoremediation system is presented in Figure 3. The POME is collected in a basin for bioremediation. The addition of appropriate microorganisms is required for the process. Microalgae consume the organic materials and oxygen created when the organic components in the POME are destroyed to perform phycoremediation. Microalgae's performance in phycoremediation leads to harvested biomass being used as a biorefinery feedstock. While the obtained liquid microalgae biomass contains nutrients and residual biomass. The material is then pumped into a pond for use

as aquaculture media. Aquaculture pond fluids containing fish excrement can be used as agricultural fertilizer in addition to producing fish. As a result, including smart eco-farming has a positive impact.

Microalgae cultivation with POME is typically done in raceway open ponds. Another option is to cultivate microalgae in photobioreactors. The microalgae *Synechococcus* (Cyanobacteria) was successfully grown in a photobioreactor with extra NPK fertilizer ⁷⁶⁾. The photobioreactors used comprise polydispersed flow on rectangular airlift with mixing performance ⁷⁷⁾.

Fig. 3: Concept of circular economy integrating system smart aquaculture, eco-farming in post POME phycoremediation

10. POME Based Biorefinery Production

The majority of studies on the environmental impact of biorefinery derived from microalgae cultivated in wastewater which is widely published have focused on biofuel. Reviews of available publications from 1999 to 2021 that LCA was used to assess the environmental impact of biofuel production. Some research has concentrated on certain bioproduct categories other than biofuels (Table 5). They concluded that, except for biopolymers, all bioproducts use less nonrenewable energy and emit fewer greenhouse gases than their fossil-based counterparts. However, they stated that it cannot be

concluded that one bioproduct outperforms others in terms of environmental performance.

However, because they used different frameworks (a border and allocation approach) and have varying levels of accuracy, transparency, and consistency, is impossible to compare their outcomes rationally⁷⁸⁾. Furthermore, the environmental evaluation of the biorefinery context is still in its early stages for two key reasons: (1) not all likely environmental issues, such as Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) are addressed, and (2) different types of uncertainty are not considered ⁷⁹⁾. As a result, environmental evaluation based on LCA is crucial in making strategic decisions about future biorefinery deployments.

Table 5: Comparison LCA of biorefinery production from microalgae

Types of biorefinery	Topic research	Boundary	Results	Ref.
Briquette	Producing energy recovery using briquette by microalgae cultivated in wastewater	Cradle to grave	Microalgae cultivated in wastewater using briquette feasible to environmentally friendly technology	⁸⁰⁾

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			and potential to produce alternative energy.	
Biochar	Biochar from microalgae	Cradle to grave	Potential to applicate in other fields.	81)
Biofuel	Biofuel production from microalgae cultivated in anaerobic digested wastewater	Cradle to grave	A promising approach could be biofuel production from microalgae combined with wastewater treatment.	82)
Bio-oil	Bio-oil production from microalgae biomass through pyrolysis processing regime	Cradle to grave	Utilization waste for microalgae nutrients were reducing the proposition's environmental impact.	83)
Biodiesel	Biodiesel from estuarine microalgae	Cradle to grave	The wastewater-biocatalyst scenario to produce biodiesel have benefit to reduce cost wastewater remediation.	84)
Biomethane	Biomethane is produced by cultured microalgae coupled to the biogas process.	Cradle to grave	Progress can be made by lowering mixing costs and increasing circulation between different production steps, or by improving the anaerobic process efficiency under controlled conditions. This new bioenergy generation process is fiercely competitive with other biofuel production processes.	85)
Biohythane	Biohythane is produced by biomass microalgae cultivated in food waste through anaerobic fermentation in the two-stage reactor.	Cradle to grave	This new bioenergy generation process is fiercely competitive with other biofuel production processes.	86)
Bioethanol	Microalgae production in a tropical country	Cradle to grave	As a result, this study predicted that microalgae-to-bioethanol conversion would have a positive impact on both energy and the environment.	87)
Biobutanol	Biobutanol is produced from genetic engineering of Cyanobacteria	Cradle to grave	A high cumulative energy demand in all scenarios indicates that this process is required to displace fossil fuels or even first and second-generation bioethanol.	88)
Bioplastic	There haven't been many LCA studies published specifically for microalgae-derived bioplastics.			89)

The problem is land availability and requirements. Large-scale biofuel production can necessitate vast tracts of land. Many countries cannot afford to divert land from agricultural production. The debate over "food vs. fuel" is complicated. Land, water, and agricultural chemicals are all required to produce food and biomass⁹⁰⁾. Food and fuel do not have to compete, especially if environmental protection and sustainable manufacturing methods are carefully planned. However, the reality is more complicated.⁹¹⁾

Microalgae for biorefinery integration into the palm oil industry can help to achieve by addressing the problems and consequences of climate change and greenhouse gas emissions, to achieve global sustainable development goals^{92,93)}. Clean energy and affordable economic growth can be achieved simultaneously through, innovation, green industry, and infrastructure. The program creates sustainability by promoting responsible production and

consumption⁹⁴⁾.

There are few studies available, which describe the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of bioplastic from microalgae.⁹⁵⁾ Microalgae biomass is one of the long-term stages toward a greener world since biorefinery made from algal biomass is more environmentally friendly.⁹⁶⁾ There are classes and species of microalgae that have yet to be recognized. As a result, the species chosen for the experiment is complicated, and more research is needed to investigate the qualities and efficiency of each species. Furthermore, algal genetic engineering experiments are restricted to the laboratory. The utilization of microalgae in biorefinery leads to the release of harmful greenhouse gases, such as carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. This issue can be mitigated by employing techniques such as incineration.^{97,98)}

Despite its high nutrient content, using POME as a growing medium for microalgae on an industrial scale

remains difficult. To begin with, the presence of a high concentration of organic components such as tannins, lignin, and phenolic compounds may be detrimental to growth²¹). High suspended solids concentrations may provide a dark coloration that could prevent light from penetrating, which is essential for developing photosynthetic organisms.^{99,100}.

Microalgae cultivation as an alternative to molecular farming techniques could aid in the development of pharmaceuticals based on natural microalgae chemicals, either directly as drugs or as essential molecules in biochemical drug production^{101,102}). Microalgae bioactive compounds can add value and boost biorefinery economic competitiveness in various applications, including the food industry, and the discovery of new enzymes and drugs. On the other hand, the utilization of microalgae cultivation products contributes to biotechnology, toxicology, and biological systems^{103,104}).

The sustainable use of microalgal biomass to produce fuel is still under investigation, with much research to be done and evaluated, even just for the cultivation stage. The results show the importance of choosing restrictions in the cultivation process to become biofuels, especially regarding energy use, fertilizer choice, water use, and microalgae composition. Improvements in various fields simultaneously can lead to rapid progress in the development of environmentally friendly microalgal biofuels. There are various advantages of treating POME with microalgae. This POME treatment approach not only decreases contaminants in wastewater; but also offers new opportunities for various applications^{105,106}).

LCA which combines economic performance, and the impact of environmental and social indicators, is the best

option for making more informed and knowledge-based decisions^{107,108}). Nonetheless, before implementing large-scale POME-integrated biorefinery production facilities and pilot-scale tests, product toxicological and techno-economic feasibility studies are required. The phrase "techno-economic analysis" (TEA) is frequently used to describe the economic benefits and technical challenges of using this biomass in a biorefinery setup^{109,110}). There are various advantages to using microalgae as a feedstock in the manufacturing of renewable fuels and products. Given the importance of cultivation productivity in the cost of producing algal biomass, more TEA analysis is needed to fully comprehend the economic potential of employing high-protein, low-cost microalgae for biorefinery conversion.

An economic analysis of the biorefinery based on the parameters listed in Table 6 was conducted. Table 6 contains the data used to conduct the economic assessment of the design chain. A discounted cash flow analysis is performed for capital cost, assuming a facility lifetime of 20 years and a 10% discount rate. Capital costs are assessed based on manufacturing capacity and equipment material, whereas operating costs comprise utilities, administrative, labor, and maintenance expenses.

Based on the amount of CO₂ and biogas effluent created by the palm oil mill and biogas plant, 112.3 t/y of dry algae are produced when grown in an open pond, whereas 2,176 t/y of dry algae are produced in a tubular photobioreactor. Open ponds have a low investment cost but limited productivity. In contrast, tubular photobioreactors have a high production cost but are efficient and produce a lot of biomass¹¹¹).

Table 6: Economic parameter of bioavailability process and product¹¹²⁾

Parameters	Classification	Value	Unit	Ref.
Biogas	Selling price	0.46	USD/m ³	113)
Electricity	Selling price	93.75	USD/MWh	114)
Biodiesel	Selling price	729.12	USD/m ³	115)
Glycerol	Selling price	1.05	USD/kg	116)
Alum	Raw material price	2.07	USD/kg	117)
Chitosan	Raw material price	2	USD/kg	116)
Hexane	Raw material price	0.47	USD/kg	116)
Isopropanol	Raw material price	1.35	USD/kg	118)
Biogas facility	Operating cost	27.65	USD/t	119)
Algae biorefinery:				
Open pond	Capital cost	34,100	USD/ha	120)
	Operating cost	14.96	USD/t	121)
Tubular photobioreactor	Capital cost	2,619	USD/m ³	122)
	Operating cost	580	USD/t	123)
Flocculation	Capital cost	2,550	USD/ha	124)
	Operating cost	15.66	USD/t	125)
Centrifugation	Capital cost	42.25	USD/t	126)
	Operating cost	2.34	USD/m ³	127)
Drying	Capital cost	112.30	USD/t	114)
	Operating cost	134.20	USD/t	128)

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Solvent extraction	Capital cost	24,300	USD/ha	¹²¹⁾
	Operating cost	4,780	USD/ha/y	¹²⁰⁾
Base catalysed transesterification and biodiesel refining	Capital cost	9,188	USD/m ³	¹²⁶⁾
	Operating cost	110.95	USD/m ³	¹²⁹⁾
Combustion	Capital cost	0.91	USD/MWh	¹¹⁴⁾

The best-performing biorefinery in terms of economic performance integrated glycerol valorization process research and development enables economically viable biorefinery schemes using *Scenedesmus dimorphus* microalgae biomass as a feedstock¹³⁰⁾, and *Desmodesmus* sp.^{79) 131)}. Economic sensitivity analyses were carried out to find additional major cost drivers; and a resource assessment comparison was carried out to analyze aspects such as water and CO₂ requirements ^{80) 132)}. Algae cultivation near point sources such as power plants as a biosequestration approach for CO₂ reduction, as well as the use of algae in nutrient recycling and environmental remediation, are increasingly developing as key study fields ^{81) 133)}. The overall results of this study showed that growing microalgae in POME to manufacture biorefinery will make it more practical by lowering the cost of production overall per unit of bioproduct.

The LCA and TEA analysis shows that using flue gas as microalgae nutrition via bio-fixation and wastewater is very profitable. As a result, these two contaminants can create microalgae, which is beneficial in a densely populated industrial setting. The investment's profitability is boosted in certain circumstances, which is critical considering the location of the microalgae biomass production plant. This is a system that will benefit not just the environment and public health (by reducing trash and GHG emissions), but also the economy (by lowering operational costs). This is the establishment of a long-term industry. The study's findings pave the way for future research, particularly modeling a full and integrated system encompassing all stakeholders ^{82) 134)}.

The exploration of the POME processing sustainability index with microalgae is currently in its early stages. As a result, combining a microalgal system with conventional POME treatment appears practical and encouraging. Because of its potential as a source of bioenergy, including microalgal culture in current POME treatment methods has become far more feasible. To optimize the socioeconomic

advantage of algae-derived biodiesel growth, places with a high socioeconomic effect multiplier should be chosen, taking regional climate, marginal land, and socioeconomic aspects into account.

Microalgal biomass has been demonstrated to be one of the most efficient and ecologically friendly alternative energy sources, serving as a realistic and sustainable source of biofuel that can help reduce atmospheric greenhouse gas emissions. The use of a biorefinery technique to extract many products from a single operating process provides the path for the development of microalgal biomass-based technologies. According to the biorefinery complexity index, one of the most promising approaches for attaining this goal is a biorefinery platform that transforms microalgal biomass into fuels, food, nutritional and feed additives, fertilizers, and pharmaceuticals¹³¹⁾.

11. Case Study Technology of Smart Agriculture

A complete overview of the various technologies that are transforming the field of smart agriculture presented in Table 7. It shows how each technology, from drones and big data analytics to blockchain and GIS, contributes differently to improving agricultural operations. These improvements provide numerous benefits, including increased efficiency, precision in resource management, improved crop monitoring, and greater decision-making capabilities. However, they present their own set of obstacles, such as high implementation costs, the need for specialized expertise, and worries about data security and privacy. Understanding these technologies in the context of their benefits and drawbacks is critical for fully realizing their promise in smart agriculture. This nuanced approach assists stakeholders in navigating the intricacies of technological integration in farming, ensuring that the transition to more intelligent agricultural systems is both sustainable and beneficial to all concerned.

Table 7: Technological Innovations in Smart Agriculture: Advantages and Challenges ¹³⁵⁾

Technology	Advantages	Challenges	Ref.
Drones	Provide aerial surveillance for crop monitoring, pest detection, and soilhealth assessment.	Require skilled operation, affected by weather conditions, and involve regulatory and privacy concerns.	¹³⁶⁾
Big DataAnalytics	Enable processing and analysis of vast datasets for predictive insights,enhancing decision-making.	Require sophisticated infrastructure, expertise in data analysis, and pose data privacy concerns.	¹³⁷⁾

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Cloud Computing	Offers scalable storage and processing power for agricultural data, accessible from anywhere.	Depend on reliable internet connectivity and raise concerns about data security and sovereignty.	^{138,139,140)}
Internet of Things (IoT)	Facilitate real-time monitoring and management of farm conditions, improving efficiency.	Need continuous internet connectivity, can be costly to implement, and have security vulnerabilities.	^{141,142)}
AI Algorithms	Automate processes, provide data-driven insights for farming operations, and enhance precision in agriculture.	Require large, quality datasets for training, potential bias in algorithms, and can be complex to integrate.	^{143,144,145,146)}
Machine Learning	Offers predictive capabilities for yield forecasting and disease detection, improving resource management.	Challenges in data acquisition and processing, accuracy of predictions, and understanding complex agricultural ecosystems.	^{147,148,149)}
Renewable Energy Solutions	Provide sustainable energy sources for powering agricultural technology, reducing carbon footprint.	Initial setup costs can be high, and efficiency can be dependent on environmental conditions.	¹⁵⁰⁾
Precision Agriculture	Enables targeted application of resources like water and fertilizers, leading to cost savings and sustainability.	High initial investment in technology and requires training for farmers to adapt to new systems.	^{141,150)}
Satellite Imagery	Offers large-scale monitoring of crop health, soil conditions, and environmental changes.	Requires access to advanced satellite data and expertise in remote sensing analysis.	¹⁵¹⁾
Robotics and Automation	Enhance efficiency in tasks like planting, harvesting, and weeding, reducing manual labor.	High cost of robotics technology, maintenance requirements, and need for technical expertise.	^{152,153,154)}
Soil and Crop Sensors	Provide precise data on soil moisture, pH levels, and crop health for informed decision-making.	Need for regular calibration, durability in different weather conditions, and initial cost.	¹⁵⁵⁾
Natural Language Processing (NLP)	Facilitates user-friendly interfaces for technology and enables local language support for farmers.	Complexity in developing accurate NLP models for different languages and dialects.	^{156,154)}
GIS and Mapping Technologies	Enable detailed spatial analysis for farm planning, resource management, and yield estimation.	Requires geospatial data expertise and integration with other farm management systems.	^{157, 154)}
Blockchain for Supply Chain	Enhances transparency and traceability in the agricultural supply chain, ensuring product authenticity.	Complexity in implementation, scalability issues, and requirement of industry-wide adoption.	¹⁵⁴⁾

12. Opportunity of Smart Aquaculture and Eco-farming Integration System Concept in POME Phycoremediation

The use of the circular economy by reusing palm oil waste, co-generating bioenergy, treating waste through microalgae cultivation, and then converting it into produce that has added value. Economic factors can be improved by extracting high-value biochemicals and developing biomaterial-based goods even further¹³²⁾. Concept of smart aquaculture and eco-farming integration system in POME phycoremediation illustrated in Figure 4a. Aquaculture is

an essential trend aimed at minimizing labor costs, enhancing operational efficiency, and increasing production. Additionally, future IoT-driven systems might aim to detect fish diseases and prevent losses in productivity. Illustrates that the Internet of Things (IoT) is an innovative and promising technology offering novel solutions across various sectors, including smart aquaculture (Figure 4b) and smart eco-farming (Figure 4c). IoT has greatly enhanced agricultural management practices, enabling connectivity among agricultural devices and equipment to optimize decisions regarding fertilizer usage and irrigation

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: (a) Illustration of smart aquaculture and eco-farming integration system concept in POME phycoremediation, (b) Overview of smart aquaculture control and monitoring system, and (c) Overview of smart eco-farming control and monitoring system

12.1. Waste components from aquaculture systems

Many researchers have described the components of waste produced by aquaculture systems. The focus of this literature review will be drawn to the principal aquaculture wastes derived from feed. Aquaculture wastes can be divided into two types: solid wastes and dissolved wastes¹³³.

12.2. Solid wastes

Unused feed and fecal droppings from farmed fish are the main sources of solid waste. They contain fish that do not survive the culturing procedure on occasion. Solid waste is further subdivided into suspended solids and settled solids. The suspended solids are small particles that remain suspended in water unless coagulation or sedimentation methods are used, and they are the most difficult type of solids to remove from culture systems. The settled solids are bigger particles that settle quickly and are easily removed from the culture column⁸².

Solid wastes are considered extremely hazardous since they can clog fish gills and cause mortality, particularly in the event of big settled particles. These wastes increase total suspended and total dissolved solids when left for an extended period and allowed to degrade. They may also enhance nitrogenous substances in the farmed fish and

stress them. Solid waste in aquaculture contains around 30% of feed waste that is easier to remove through recirculating aquaculture systems than in flow-through systems¹⁵⁸.

12.3. Dissolved wastes

Dissolved waste is the result of fish metabolism or uneaten feed. The two most important components of concern in dissolved wastes are nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) products. These two elements are necessary for the production of protein, which is the fundamental component of fish diet. Fish, regardless of species, require a high crude protein level in their diet, ranging from 25 to 50%. heavy-protein fish diets are heavy in nitrogen and phosphorus, and the fish retains less than half of these potential water contaminants (nitrogen and phosphorus¹⁵⁹).

Nitrogen is primarily evacuated as dissolved ammonia, while phosphorus is excreted as particulates. Aquaculture has a high potential for environmental pollution since fish are unable to utilize a large amount of N and P, the key nutrients (components) of the diet. As a result, it is classified as industrial waste. These nutrients enter the body and are then eliminated as waste. When these nutrients enter the water, they can harm fish and other aquatic life⁸¹). These chemical components have the potential to serve as fertilizer in agricultural systems⁸⁴.

Combining coagulation-flocculation and membrane techniques can reduce POME effluent pollution¹⁶⁰).

12.4. Smart Eco-farming Using Waste of Aquaculture

Economic prosperity in recent times has been concentrated in the fields of information technology and farm software development¹⁶¹). To achieve meaningful progress, particularly in a given area, the strategy should prioritize the following goals: protecting natural resources, maximizing resource efficiency, boosting productivity and profitability, and enhancing quality and competitiveness by lowering production costs. The idea behind integrated fish farming is to gradually combine two or more typically independent farming systems to create a larger farming system that primarily focuses on fish. An integrated, or triple-A, system consists of farming, aquaculture, and agriculture and is cost-effective and self-sufficient. This kind of farming provides very good resource efficiency when it comes to transferring waste or byproducts from one system to another. To maximize output, it also makes it possible to use available farming space effectively¹⁶²).

Result of incorporating smart eco-farming, there is a sustainable environmental system, often known as a circular economy. This technology is more cost-effective than biorefinery production because microalgae biomass is used directly, eliminating the requirement for costs associated with the biomass utilization process. Smart aquaculture and eco-farming can be employed as an alternative method in the usage of POME and microalgae that are more practical and economical to create opportunities to make sustainable production operations¹⁶¹).

In recent decades, aquaculture has emerged as the fastest-growing food production industry. The supply-demand gap for fish is constantly growing, and dwindling freshwater availability is becoming a key constraint on productivity. Investigating alternative water sources, such as treated wastewater (TWW), is becoming a popular technique for meeting agriculture's increasing water demand. People have been reusing wastewater (TWW) for agriculture and aquaculture for centuries¹⁶²).

According to research, fish are safe for human food in terms of microbiological contamination and heavy metal and organic micropollutant bioaccumulation, with levels found to be within international human consumption guidelines. Furthermore, employing TWW as an alternate water source for aquaculture has both economic and ecological benefits⁵⁰). Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) are water-efficient, eco-friendly, and highly productive intensive farming systems¹⁶³).

The aquaculture technique is critical for eco farmers who struggle to obtain fertilizer due to high costs. It is crucial since this form of farming is organic, eco-friendly, and long-term¹⁶⁴). Aquaculture waste is put into the soil directly and will be generated in the integrated farming system (IFS) as a result of integration that is called an eco-farming system centered on attempts to protect and preserve nature by utilizing organic waste products as agricultural media¹⁶⁵).

Animal and plant waste is put into the soil directly or by composting, as a substantial amount of agricultural waste will be generated in the IFS as a result of integration, and it aids in the improvement of the soil's physical, chemical, and biological health. The implementation of IFS technology on a large scale throughout India will improve and sustain small and marginal farmers' livelihoods, allowing them to double their revenue on the same plot of land while improving employment and meeting the nutritional needs of the farm family^{166,167,168}).

The research study proved the usefulness of smart farming in improving and increasing agricultural productivity to help close the food demand gap. The Internet of Things (IoT) is widely regarded as the foundation of smart agriculture technology since it connects all components of smart systems, not only in agriculture but also in other applications¹⁶⁹). In agriculture, IoT can be used in a range of disciplines such as farm monitoring, irrigation¹⁷⁰) pest management^{171,172}), harvesting, and so on^{173,174}). Based on the literature that has been studied, it can compare social, economic, and environmental aspects of smart farming and conventional farming, the results of which are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Comparison of Smart Farming and Conventional Farming in social, economic, and environmental aspects

Aspects	Smart Farming	Conventional Farming	Ref.
Social	The agricultural tools used are already in the form of machines. Such as tractors, planting machines, fertilizer machines, drones, irrigation machines, and harvesting machines. Machine tools are run automatically so they do not require much labour. On the downside, smart farming reduces employment because it is operated by experts.	The agricultural tools used are still very simple and are operated by many laborers, providing employment opportunities for the community.	175)
Economy	Modern equipment is costly, but efficient and increases agricultural production.	The processing and operation of the tools do not cost much, but it is inefficient, and agricultural production is low.	176, 177) 178) 179)

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Environment	The concept of using organic materials so as not to damage the soil and environmentally friendly agriculture that can be sustainable.	The concept of using inorganic materials that in the long run damage the soil resulting in agriculture that is not environmentally friendly and consequently unsustainable.	180,181,182)
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An integrated multi-trophic aquaculture business that combined fed aquaculture with organic extractive aquaculture saw a 20% rise in shellfish production and a profit increase of more than 230%, according to the study's findings. and 68%, in comparison to separate monocultures of shellfish and finfish. Using a variety of trophic level organisms, it has been noted that these creative integrated technological practices in aquaculture are a sustainable development in the aquaculture industry because they maximize nutrient uptake, enhance water quality, and possibly generate more revenue. The primary obstacles to this sustainable system are the need for a large amount of land for farming and the difficulties in coordinating many species, both of which call for additional technical innovations that can overcome the constraints^{183,184}.

POME-based bioenergy with microalgae has received a lot of attention.⁵⁵ Smart aquaculture and eco-farming have yet to be researched. As a result, these problems are being studied to find novel methods for POME use. Smart farming is also known as smart agriculture in Indonesia. This is a farming method that makes use of technology. For example, the use of a platform linked to a tablet or smartphone device. Furthermore, smart farming makes farming activities more environmentally friendly. The idea is to make agricultural data collection easier. Easily obtain field data such as soil nutrient status, air humidity, meteorological conditions, and so on. Food security should become easier to attain as technology advances in the 4.0 era. Smart farming in developing nations enables real-time analysis and mapping of soil features, as well as proper decision management. Finally, smart farming in developing nations needs increasing support from governments, small farms, and the business sector.

13. Implementation of Smart Aquaculture and Eco-farming

The implementation discussed in this study is an example of implementation outcomes from handling trash other than POME because there is no literature on POME handling for smart agriculture. India has conducted machine learning to sort rice grains using machine learning (ML) algorithms. The simulation results show that the suggested ML method outperforms the conventional machine, developing predictive models. This technique outperforms current machine learning-based classifiers in terms of computational efficiency and accuracy while sorting rice grains. The main gain is increased productivity, but the drawback is a lack of contemporary

solutions to address climate change^{185,186}.

The implementation of smart farming has been done in Thailand using the Solar Water Pumping Irrigation System (SWPS) in plantation and agricultural irrigation systems to enhance food security. The use of SWPS to supply water for irrigation has shown to be successful and efficient. This technology is affordable to maintain and simple to use. In agricultural and plantation settings, where diesel pump usage is necessary due to relatively high demand, the implementation of SWPS is also significantly less expensive. Farmers profit from applying SWPS irrigation systems in several ways, including higher agricultural product productivity, increased revenue, improved product quality, and increased process efficiency¹⁸⁷.

The advancements in technology have had a variety of impacts on the agricultural sector. The foundation of artificial intelligence is the idea that it can characterize human intelligence in a way that a computer can replicate it for a variety of tasks, both basic and complicated. Artificial intelligence seeks to accomplish the following: learning, thinking, and perception. The adoption of several complex models (deep learning methodology and machine learning) has transformed farming into digital farming. Farm management systems are evolving into full artificial intelligence systems through the integration of ML with sensor data. These systems provide sophisticated recommendations and insights for future decisions and actions, ultimately aimed at optimizing productivity^{188,189}. Agriculture, whether traditional or modern, has the opportunity to become an agritourism area today. The growth of agritourism, which promotes higher income, is at last able to retain young people employed in the agricultural industry. The communities' ultimate choice would protect their property and inspire youth to pursue careers in tourism and agriculture^{190,191}

Make a significant contribution to the agricultural industry by offering a hydroponics system that is sustainable and requires little or no electricity. By doing this, we can utilize this technology not only in metropolitan but also in rural places to develop an agricultural system that uses hydroponics to harness the potential of solar power for heat maintenance¹⁹². Crop drying is typically done with sunshine, however with smart farming, rice drying may be done using an electrohydrodynamic drying system^{193,194}. Drying with coal fuel heating and identification of coal pulverizer anomalies using a long short-term memory (LSTM) and autoencoder (AE)¹⁹⁵. Smart farming system monitoring can make use of power monitoring for on-grid photovoltaic systems via a low-cost, open-source IoT platform¹⁹⁶. Sustainable smart farming, in addition to

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having a plan for feeding animals¹⁹⁷). The microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Spirulina platensis* culture consortium is a possible cathode compartment, whereas the anode compartment is filled with artificial tempe (fermented soybean cake) effluent containing indigenous bacteria capable of decomposing organic molecules^{198,199}. Smart farming is a sustainable agriculture system that supports the Industry 4.0 program. Several forms of study have been conducted to map the interlinkages between Industry 4.0 and Sustainability, although disciplinary prisms frequently neglect the social dimension of sustainability. Nonetheless, the technologically driven character of Industry 4.0 technologies, along with the relatively early stage of their lifecycle, brings to the forefront several challenges that are highlighted in triple-bottom-line categorization. Economic consequences include the high cost and complexities of assessing financial benefits and economic effectiveness. Environmental consequences may include concerns such as increased e-waste, increased energy consumption, deforestation, and environmental deterioration caused by industrialization and unsustainable economic decisions²⁰⁰. Social consequences may include subtle effects on communities as a result of the intentional or unintentional use of technology). Human-robot interface challenges, unemployment risks, and privacy concerns are only a few of the social implications²⁰¹.

14. Conclusions

The conclusions that can be obtained from this literature study are several strains of microalgae species can be cultivated in POME to remove pollutants, namely *Chlamydomonas sp*, *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Nannochloropsis oculata*, *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*, *Chlorella sp*, *Spirulina platensis*, *Chlorella sorokiniana* and *Arthrospira platensis*. However, the success of POME wastewater treatment by microalgae depends on its cultivation technique, selection of suitable species and environmental conditions that promote growth.

Generally, research on microalgae cultivation in POME is still at the laboratory scale level. So there is still no one who has carried out a sustainability analysis through LCA. More research is needed to use an appropriate, sustainable, and cost-effective cultivation system to transform microalgae biomass into value-added products.

The majority of studies on the environmental impact of biorefinery derived from microalgae cultivated in wastewater which is widely published have focused on bioenergy. However, bioenergy-based biorefineries are difficult to sustain due to high production costs.

Based on the data and information gathered regarding the large amounts of POME in Indonesia and other countries, the adoption of large-scale smart aquaculture and eco-farming is particularly helpful, as monitoring can be done

promptly and efficiently. The implementation of new model smart farming systems in developing nations requires greater support from the government at the low farm level and the business sector.

15. Recommendation

Microalgae-based POME processing research is still in its early stages. As a result, combining a microalgal system with traditional POME treatment appears to be both promising and practicable. Given its potential for bioenergy production, incorporating microalgal culture into existing POME treatment systems has become much more viable. To optimize the socioeconomic advantage of microalgae-based biorefinery development, places with a high socioeconomic effect multiplier should be selected, taking into account regional climate, marginal land, and socioeconomic characteristics. Microalgal biomass is one of the most efficient and environmentally friendly alternative energy sources, as well as a promising and sustainable source of biofuel capable of reducing atmospheric greenhouse gas emissions, microalgal biomass is a highly efficient and ecologically friendly alternative bioavailable source. The use of a biorefinery technique that recovers many products from a single operating process allows for the development of microalgal biomass-based technologies. According to the biorefinery complexity index, converting microalgal biomass into fuels, food, nutritional and feed supplements, fertilizers, and pharmaceuticals is one of the most promising approaches for attaining this aim.

Smart farming is a sustainable agricultural system that complements the Industry 4.0 initiative. Several types of research have been performed to map the interconnections between Industry 4.0 and Sustainability. However, disciplinary prisms usually overlook the social dimension of sustainability. Nonetheless, the technologically driven nature of Industry 4.0 technologies, together with their relatively early stage of development, brings to the forefront certain issues identified in triple-bottom-line categorization. Economic repercussions include the high expense and complexity of determining financial benefits and economic effectiveness. Environmental consequences may include concerns such as increasing e-waste, higher energy consumption, deforestation, and environmental degradation induced by industrialization and unsustainable economic decisions.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Nomenclature

AE	Autoencoder
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
C	Carbon
°C	Celsius degree
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
CPO	Crude Palm Oil
FFB	Fresh Fruit Bunches
g/L	gram per liter
HPBR	Hybrid Photobioreactor
HRAPs	High-Rate Algal Ponds
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
IFS	Integrated Farming System
IoT	Internet of Things
K lux	K = First Initial of Mr. Keshra Bhudia Lux = Nickname of Mrs. Laxmi Bhudia
L	Liter
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
L/D cycle	liter per day
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
mg/L	milligram per liter
ml	milliliter
mol	a common scientific unit for measuring huge numbers of very small substances, such as atoms, molecules, or other specific particles.
MJ	megajoule
N	Nitrogen
NaHCO ₃	Sodium bicarbonate
O	Oxygen
P	Phosphate
PHB	Photobioreactor
POME	Palm Oil Mill Effluent
ppm	Part per million
PUFA	Polyunsaturated Fatty Acid
RAS	Recirculating Aquaculture Systems
SFA	Sales Force Automation
SWPS	Solar Water Pumping Irrigation System
TEA	Techno-economic Analysis
TN	Total Nitrogen
TP	Total Phosphate
TWW	Treated Wastewater
Coelastrella sp. UKM4	The name of <i>Coelastrella</i> sp. strain
W	Watt

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